

MAX phases triggered in-situ TiC and γ' -Ni₃(Al,Ti) synergistically reinforced nickel matrix composite

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Abstract

A novel type of in-situ TiC- γ' reinforced composites were successfully fabricated using pure Ni and Ti₂AlC powder mixtures by hot-press sintering technology. Detailed interfacial analysis was carried out using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM). The size and morphology of heterogeneous TiC- γ' which have critically influenced mechanical properties can be tailored by thermal treatment process. The TiC- γ' /Ni composites fabricated under 1200 °C with subsequent solution and aging treatments exhibit tensile strength of ~1300 MPa with ~6.2% ductility. The superior combination of strength and ductility can be attributed to the more homogenous distribution and location of ultrafine TiC (100-700 nm) and γ' (~50 nm) nanoparticles in the Ni matrix, which played a synergistic effect on determining the enhanced mechanical behaviors.

Research on the reaction mechanism in the Ti₂AlC-Ni system

Reaction equation:

Topological transformation:

In-situ composite:

γ' will precipitate out from Ni matrix when the content of Ti₂AlC exceeds 28vol%

Microstructural characterization on TiC- γ' /Ni composite

SEM images of 30vol.% Ti₂AlC/Ni composite(a-c) and 40vol.% Ti₂AlC/Ni composite, illustrating the morphology of TiC, γ' and Ni grains, respectively.

High-resolution TEM images on interfaces of TiC/Ni and Ni₃(Al,Ti)/Ni and evolution of γ' in γ matrix after heat treatment

TEM results of the TiC- γ' /Ni composite. (a): STEM images of highlighted TiC embedded in Ni matrix; (b): High-resolution TEM images on interface of TiC/Ni, the insets are FFT patterns of Ni and TiC; (c): FFT-filtered image of TiC/Ni interface; (d): FFT pattern of TiC/Ni interface. (e): Inverse FFT image by masking the circled diffraction spots in (d), the misfit dislocations are illustrated by the inclined letter T; (f): Distributions of γ' precipitate in the γ -Ni matrix; (g): High-resolution TEM image of the γ'/γ interface, the inset is {001} superlattice reflection of γ' precipitate; (h): FFT-filtered image of γ'/γ interface; (i): Schematic illustrations of the unit cell of γ' phase.

(a)-(c) microstructures of the TiC- γ' /Ni composite, (d)-(f) distributions of γ' after solute treatment and aging for 20h, 50h and 100h. (g)-(i) the higher magnification of γ' precipitates corresponding to (d)-(f).

TiC/Ni Semi-Coherent: $(020)\text{TiC} // (111)\text{Ni}$, $[001]\text{TiC} // [011]\text{Ni}$
 Ni/Ni₃(Al,Ti) Coherent: $\{100\}_{\gamma'} // \{100\}_{\gamma}$, $\langle 010 \rangle_{\gamma'} // \langle 010 \rangle_{\gamma}$

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